

The Centre for Sustainable Ocean Science (SOS) was established at Åbo Akademi University (ÅAU) in January 2024. SOS is a transdisciplinary research centre whose mission is to provide knowledge on wicked problems linked to marine biodiversity and its role in the societal transition to sustainability. SOS is one of four ÅAU Centres of Excellence in Research funded during 2024–2028 by the Åbo Akademi University Foundation. The ÅAU Centre of Excellence program has been ongoing since 2006 and it supports research at the university with the aim of achieving the highest possible quality and impact. SOS is led by Director **Anna Törnroos-Remes** and Vice Director **Nina Tynkkynen**, supported by a steering group of lead researchers within the centre and an international scientific advisory board (see annex for members).

The overarching research questions of SOS are: when and how do human actions interact with marine biodiversity in creating wicked problems, and what can be done to solve such challenges? The inter- and transdisciplinary research includes environmental and marine biology, political science, chemistry, industrial management, law, and the arts. The work is structured around six workpackages: WPs 1–3 include specific case-studies, while WPs 4–6 draw on their work, support them, and synthesize their findings.

The six SOS workpackages.

Recruitments and WP progress

During November and December 2023, following a positive funding decision from the Åbo Akademi University Foundation and in preparation for the Center’s launch, SOS recruited Research Assistant **Malla Lehtonen** to work fulltime on coordinating the center’s activities and communications over the coming five-year period.

At the start of 2024 SOS initiated work within each of the six workpackages according to the centre’s research plan. During the spring term, WP1 (*Healthy and clean seas*) recruited postdoctoral researcher **Henri Sumelius** for a six-month period to study littoral biodiversity and biodiversity loss along the Finnish coast. This work contributed to the [Finnish Nature Panel’s report](#) on marine biodiversity loss in coastal areas of Finland (published March 2024) and was later published in [Ambio – A Journal of Environment and Society](#) (May 2025).

In the autumn term, WP2 (*Food production*) recruited postdoctoral researcher **Roxana Preston** to study implementing genetic diversity into charophyte restoration to inform and improve restoration practices, and WP3 (*Land-sea interaction*) recruited postdoctoral researcher **Conny Sjöqvist** to map pressures in the SOS case study region. Further recruitments at the end of the year led to the following researchers joining SOS in early 2025: postdoctoral researcher **Susanna Jernberg** to

study ecosystem services in the SOS case study area (WP1), doctoral researcher **Thaysa Portela de Carvalho** to research offshore wind development in the archipelago and especially the Åland region (WP3), and postdoctoral researcher **Einat Amir** to study and facilitate the art-science collaborations within SOS (WP5).

During autumn 2024, WP4 (*Transitions towards holistic marine governance and improved regulations*) initiated internal *Governance Clinics* with WP1–3 to identify specific governance-related challenges within the case studies. WP5 (*Theory and methodology*) organized an internal *Co-creation Workshop* for the other SOS work packages to reflect on the aims and methods for transdisciplinary co-creation. WP6 (*Science engagement, collaboration, and impact*) launched the Sea Hub Network, a pre-initiative by the ÅAU strategic research profiling area The Sea that is now built further within SOS. The objective of the network is to expand and strengthen our international community of marine researchers and research institutions. The network's inaugural meeting was held online on 1st October with around 20 attendees from Finland, Sweden, Denmark, and the Netherlands.

WP6 also realized the first of three SOS Project Booster funding calls, which aim to foster collaboration and to support the exploration of innovative ideas and preliminary research questions related to SOS's mission. The call was open from 1st October to 15th November and received 12 applications. In the decisions given out on 15th December, the evaluation board – consisting of SOS steering group members excluding those with conflicts of interest, as well as one external member – awarded a total of 45 800 euros in funding to the following four projects:

- *Saving the Baltic Sea with law?* (10 000 €)
Lead: Laura Ervo, Professor in Procedural Law, Örebro University and ÅAU
- *Meanings of archipelago forests. A co-productive art-science project with two archipelago secondary schools* (10 800 €)
Lead: Otso Kortekangas, Researcher in History, ÅAU
- *Escape the heat: Microclimates and Heatwaves* (5 000 €)
Lead: Sarah Rühmkorff, Doctoral Researcher in Environmental and Marine Biology, ÅAU
- *Modeling advanced primary production scenarios in coastal seas – MIMOSA* (20 000 €)
Lead: Conny Sjöqvist, Postdoctoral Researcher in Environmental and Marine Biology, ÅAU

All of the funded projects will be carried out during 2025. The remaining two SOS Project Booster calls are scheduled to take place in late 2025 and 2026 (tentatively).

Collaborations

In April 2024, SOS joined The Baltic Sea Challenge, a network started by the cities of Turku and Helsinki that invites organizations to commit to the protection of the Baltic Sea. The network currently includes 330 organizations from Finland and other Baltic Sea countries.

In August, researchers from SOS and other Åbo Akademi University units launched a 1,5-year project with Meyer Turku. The project addresses the new regulation on biodiversity reporting which, from 2025 onwards, requires companies to disclose their impacts and dependencies associated with biodiversity. The overall aim is to provide a basis for a biodiversity program that includes both short- and long-term action points to mitigate Meyer Turku Shipyard's impacts on biodiversity. The project is a part of their larger research and development effort NEcOLEAP.

To officially establish SOS as part of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development 2021–2030 (Ocean Decade), the centre applied for endorsement in the Ocean Decade’s autumn call for Decade Actions and received a positive decision in early 2025. This endorsement is a recognition that the work carried out in SOS will play a central role in supporting the Ocean Decade mission to provide transformative ocean science solutions for sustainable development, connecting people and our ocean. It also marks an important milestone in the current five-year action plan of SOS and connects the centre to a global network of ocean experts. While the Ocean Decade is not a funding body, endorsed Actions benefit from increased visibility, collaboration opportunities, and support that can help unlock new resources. SOS is endorsed as an [Ocean Decade Project](#) under the programme [Global Ecosystem for Ocean Solutions \(GEOS\)](#), led by Ocean Visions.

Additional collaborations were initiated through various projects and efforts with, for example, Wave Riders – The Interdisciplinary Network for Environmental Humanities (Aallonharjalle, AHA) at the University of Turku, the Water and Environmental Engineering Research Group at Turku University of Applied Sciences, the blue economy innovation company A’Pelago, the Finnish national branch of the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR), and Finland’s Maritime Spatial Planning cooperation group.

Outreach

On June 8th—World Ocean Day—SOS officially launched its website and social media channels, including LinkedIn, Instagram, and Facebook. In line with Åbo Akademi University’s decision to leave X (formerly Twitter) in November, SOS also discontinued its own X account. To stay connected, SOS maintains two mailing lists: one for general updates on the centre’s activities and another dedicated to communications within the Sea Hub Network.

The centre’s official kick-off event took place on 10–11 September at the Sibelius Museum and Åbo Akademi University, drawing approximately 100 participants both in person and online. The program featured short presentations by SOS researchers and key collaborators, along with keynote speeches from SOS Advisory Board members **Rachel Kelly** and **Jörn Schmidt**.

Throughout 2024, SOS organized over a dozen events aimed at both the research community and the general public. Among these were the monthly *Sea Seminars* organized together with the ÅAU research profiling area [The Sea](#). These hybrid seminars explore diverse topics in marine and sustainability research, featuring speakers from SOS, ÅAU, and a range of external partners and stakeholders. The series continues into 2025.

SOS was invited to give a presentation at the first national Marine Spatial Planning Days in Helsinki in November. Organized by the Finnish MSP Coordination in collaboration with key partners, the event gathered around 100 participants. SOS contributed with a workshop focused on the biodiversity impacts of offshore wind farms, feeding directly into Thaysa Portela de Carvalho’s ongoing research in WP3.

SOS researchers also showcased the centre’s work to the wider public at two major events: the Baltic Sea Day celebrations in Turku on 29th August and the Turku Book Fair in October. Both occasions sparked significant interest in the centre’s work and mission.

ANNEX

SOS Steering Group

Anna Törnroos-Remes (SOS Director; Assoc. Prof. (tenure track), PhD, Environmental and Marine Biology, ÅAU)

Nina Tynkkynen (SOS Vice Director & WP5 Lead; Prof., PhD, Public Administration, ÅAU)

Christoffer Boström (SOS WP1 Lead; Assoc. Prof., PhD, Environmental and Marine Biology, ÅAU)

Sonja Salovius-Laurén (SOS WP2 Lead; University Researcher, PhD, Environmental and Marine Biology, ÅAU)

Magnus Hellström (SOS WP3 Lead; Prof., Dr (Tech.), Industrial Management, ÅAU)

Henrik Ringbom (SOS WP4 Lead; Prof., PhD, Maritime Law, ÅAU)

Christian Pansch-Hattich (SOS WP6 Lead; Prof., PhD, Environmental and Marine Biology, ÅAU)

Cecilia Lundberg (Education Planner, PhD, Centre for Lifelong Learning, ÅAU)

Taru Elfving (Curator, Researcher, PhD, CAA Contemporary Art Archipelago)

Pasi Tolvanen (Researcher, PhD, Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry and Reaction Engineering, ÅAU)

*Tapio Salmi (Prof., Dr (Tech.), Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry and Reaction Engineering, ÅAU)
In May 2025, Salmi stepped down and Dr. Pasi Tolvanen joined the SOS steering group in his place.*

SOS Advisory Board

Dr. Marina Panova (Deputy Director, Centre for Sea and Society, Univ. of Gothenburg)

Dr. Thorsten Blenckner (Assoc. Prof. & Principal Researcher, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm Univ.)

Dr. Niko Soininen (Prof., Univ. of Eastern Finland; Assoc. Prof., HELSUS, Univ. of Helsinki)

Dr. Rachel Kelly (Researcher, Centre for Marine Socioecology, Univ. of Tasmania; Knowledge Broker, Aquaculture Council of Western Australia Inc.)

Dr. Jörn Schmidt (Director for Sustainable Aquatic Food Systems, WorldFish)